

Nanoporous VO₂ (M) Thin Films via Lyophilization with Enhanced Luminous Transmittance and Solar Modulating Ability

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Abstract

Vanadium dioxide is the most widely researched thermochromic material with phase transition temperature (τ_c) at around 68 °C and its thermochromic performance can be enhanced by adding nanoporosity. Freeze drying has been employed to fabricate nanostructures with different porosities from 16 to 45 % by varying the pre-freezing temperature and precursor concentration. The luminous transmittance (T_{lum}) and solar modulating ability (ΔT_{sol}) are greatly enhanced as a result of increasing pore size and pore density. The freeze-dried sample with 7.5 mL H₂O₂ precursor dip-coated at 300 mm/min gives the best combination of thermochromic properties ($T_{lum} \approx 50\%$, $\Delta T_{sol} = 14.7\%$), which surpasses the best combined thermochromic performance reported to date that we are aware of ($T_{lum} \approx 41\%$, $\Delta T_{sol} = 14.1\%$).

Keywords: Nanoporous; vanadium dioxide; freeze drying; thermochromic properties.

1. Introduction

Vanadium dioxide (VO_2) exhibits a fully reversible transition from insulating monoclinic phase ($P2_1/c$) to metallic rutile phase ($P4_2/mnm$) at around 68°C [1]. The metal-insulator transition (MIT) can be characterized by the dramatic change in the optical properties of VO_2 thin films [2]. When numerous dopants are introduced into its crystal lattice via various methods, VO_2 is able to transit the phase at around room temperature ($\tau_c \approx 25^\circ\text{C}$) [3], hence becoming an ideal choice as the coating material for smart windows.[4-7] For practical applications, the major challenge for VO_2 -based coatings is to improve the luminous transmittance (T_{lum}) and solar modulating ability (the ability to regulate the input solar energy, ΔT_{sol}) simultaneously.[8]

Amongst the reported methods, only a few can achieve enhanced T_{lum} with little sacrifice of ΔT_{sol} . Some of the reported methods include doping certain ions (such as Mg^{2+} [9] and Eu^{3+} [10]) into the VO_2 crystal lattice, fabricating a multilayered structure ($\text{TiO}_2/\text{VO}_2/\text{TiO}_2/\text{VO}_2/\text{TiO}_2$) [11], and applying antireflection (AR) coatings, such as TiO_2 and Si-Al gel top layers [12-14]. It was proposed that pores with air can be considered as a secondary component, thus nanoporous VO_2 films could enhance both T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} by increasing the density of pores [13]. This was confirmed by Kang et. al. [14] who used polymer-assisted deposition to produce nanoporous film with an ~ 28 nm mean pore size, and gave one of the best reported results ($T_{\text{lum}} \approx 41\%$, $\Delta T_{\text{sol}} = 14.1\%$) in the literature as shown in **Table 1**. The fabrication of periodic porous structure and use of sol-gel method followed by evaporation have also been reported to produce nanoporous structures with improved properties, and their properties are listed in **Table 1**. When sols are frozen at low temperature and low pressure, solvents will sublime and get removed by vacuum to produce as-obtained nanoporous SiO_2 and Al_2O_3 cryogels via lyophilization (freeze drying) [17-23]. Freeze-drying is widely used in chemical synthesis and the food-processing industry; therefore, it is readily scalable. In this study, we report a facile method to fabricate nanoporous VO_2 (M) thin films with the best thermochromic properties ($T_{\text{lum}} \approx 50\%$, $\Delta T_{\text{sol}} = 14.7\%$), via dip-coating of solution precursors followed by lyophilization of samples.

Table 1: Summary of ways to fabricate nanoporous VO₂ thin films and their optical properties

Synthesis method	T_{lum}	ΔT_{sol}	Mean pore size
Polymer-assisted deposition * [16]	~ 41%	14.1%	28 nm
Sol-gel [24] (V ₂ O ₅ -H ₂ O ₂ precursor)	~ 40%	2.2%	Elongated pores surrounded at grain boundaries, ~ 100 nm in width
Solution infiltration [25] (periodic porous structure)	70.2%	7.9%	~ 200 nm
Sol-gel [26] (CTAV-BuOH precursor)	46.5%	Unreported	~ 500 nm

* This is the best reported combination of thermochromic properties prior to this report.

2. Experimental section

The chemicals used in this study were vanadium (V) oxide (V₂O₅, 99.99%, Alfa Aesar), hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30 wt%, VWR) and oxalic acid dihydrate ((COOH)₂·2H₂O, 99.5%, VWR). All of the above-mentioned chemicals were used as received without any further purification.

Figure 1 shows a schematic flow chart (not to scale) for the synthesis of nanoporous thin film samples through lyophilization and control samples via evaporation. The powder precursors were dissolved in solution to form sol followed by gelation to form a more rigid structure, and the solution was dip-coated onto the fused silica substrates. The solvent between the gels was evaporated at room temperature to obtain the control sample and freeze-dried to obtain large-pore structures.

Figure 1: Schematic flowchart (side view, not to scale) for the synthesis of a control sample via evaporation (ambient drying) and nanoporous samples via lyophilization (freeze-drying).

2.1 Synthesis of coatings

V_2O_5 powder (182 mg) was dissolved in different volumes (7.5, 10.0, 12.5, 15.0, and 17.5 mL) of H_2O_2 and vigorously stirred at 70 °C. When a reddish-brown sol was formed, 400 mg of oxalic acid was added. The mixture was continuously stirred until a clear blue solution of VO^{2+} was obtained [27]. The as-obtained solution was filtered to remove any undissolved oxalic acid. The final precursor was dip-coated onto a $15 \times 15 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^3$ precleaned fused silica substrate using a dip coater (KSV Instruments Limited) at various withdrawal rates (100, 200, and 300 mm/min). After the sample was dried under ambient conditions, one side of the coating was carefully wiped off using a wet cotton bud.

2.2 Freeze drying of thin films

The single-side coated thin film was contained in a 50 mL centrifuge tube (Corning Inc.), which was covered with a piece of filter paper and sealed using parafilm. It was then placed in a 300 mL freeze drying flask (Fisher Scientific), frozen in a freezer (MDF-U537, Sanyo) at various temperatures (-20 and -30 °C) for 3 h before loading onto the lyophilizer (FreeZone 2.5 Plus, Labconco) for 24 h freeze drying. The lyophilizer collector was set at -80 °C and 0.01 mbar.

2.3 Heat treatment of samples

After being freeze-dried, the sample was immediately removed from the centrifuge tube and annealed at 550 °C for 2 h in a tube furnace with argon (99.9995%, NOX) atmosphere ^[10]. The ramping rate was set to 1.0 °C/min, and gas flow rate was tuned to around 200 cm³/min. The as-obtained VO₂ thin films were light bronze in color.

2.4 Characterization method

The XRD patterns were examined using a Shimadzu XRD-6000 X-ray diffractometer (Cu K_α, $\lambda=0.15406$ nm produced under a 40 kV voltage and a 30 mA current) at an X-ray grazing angle of 1.0°. The surface morphologies of the samples were viewed under a JEOL JSM-6340F field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, accelerating voltage 5 kV). The porosity based on FESEM images was calculated using Origin Pro 9. The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern were obtained using a Carl Zeiss LIBRA[®] 120 in-column energy filter TEM (accelerating voltage 120 kV) equipped with an integrated OMEGA filter. The transmittance spectra were collected using an Agilent Cary 5000 UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer, which was equipped with a Linkam PE120 system peltier simple heating and cooling stage for the former and a diffuse reflectance accessory (DRA) for the latter. The calculations of integrated luminous transmittance (T_{lum} , $280 \leq \lambda \leq 780$ nm) and solar transmittance (ΔT_{sol} , $250 \leq \lambda \leq 2500$ nm) can be found in an earlier publication ^[28]. The thickness was measured on a KLA-Tencor Alpha-Step IQ surface profiler, and the recorded value was averaged from five measured points with ~20% variation due to the nonuniformity of the dip-coated samples. A simple cross-cut test (ASTM 3359-08) has been performed to test the coating adhesion, and the results show that the sintered samples are classified as 5B, which indicates excellent adhesion to the substrate as a result of the high-temperature annealing.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Effects of pre-freezing and freeze-drying on thermochromic properties

The samples were dip-coated using the precursor with 15.0 mL H₂O₂ at a withdrawal rate of 100 mm/min and were pre-frozen at different temperatures (-20 °C or -30 °C) for 3 h. The XRD patterns revealed a peak at $2\theta \approx 28.0^\circ$ as shown in **Figure 2**, that can be ascribed to (011) plane of monoclinic VO₂ (JCPDS no.: 82-661). The grain size is estimated to be ~91 nm using the Debye–Scherrer method. Different prefreezing temperatures and freeze-drying processes have no influence on the phase formation compared to that of control samples. The formation of a pure VO₂ (M) phase by oxalic acid reduction is similar to that in the literature in the absence of acid in the precursor [29–31].

Figure 2: XRD patterns of samples coated using 15.0 mL H₂O₂ precursor: (a) control, without pre-freezing and freeze drying; (b) freeze-drying without pre-freezing; (c) pre-frozen at -20 °C followed by freeze-drying and (d) pre-frozen at -30 °C followed by freeze-drying.

The transmittance and reflectance spectra are shown in **Figure 3**. In contrast to the control sample, freeze-drying increases the transmittance at all wavelengths (250–2500 nm) at both 20 and 90 °C, which is reflected in enhanced T_{lum} and T_{sol} (**Table 2**). For samples without prefreezing,

transmittance within the visible range (380–780 nm) at 20 °C is generally lower than that at 90 °C; as the prefreezing temperature decreases, the intersection point (inset of **Figure 3a**) of the two spectra shows a blue shift and T_{lum} at 20 °C exceeds that at 90 °C. This reveals a similar trend to that of the interference effect,³² which leads to an increase in ΔT_{lum} , thereby giving a higher ΔT_{sol} (**Table 2**)^[16].

Figure 3: (a) Transmittance, (b) reflectance, and (c) $1 - T\% - R\%$ spectra of the control (black lines); freeze-drying without prefreezing (red lines); with -20 °C prefreezing (blue lines) and -30 °C prefreezing (purple lines) samples coated using 15.0 mL of H_2O_2 precursor. Transmittance spectra were collected at both 20 and 90 °C, but reflectance spectra were collected only at 20 °C.

Table 2: Effects of pre-freezing and freeze drying on thermochromic properties of thin films

Pre-freezing temperature (°C)	Freeze drying	T_{lum} (20/90 °C)	ΔT_{lum}	T_{sol} (20/90 °C)	ΔT_{sol}	Porosity
None *	None	55.2%/58.2%	-3.0%	61.8%/58.9%	2.9%	2%
None	Yes	63.0%/62.6%	0.4%	68.5%/64.3%	4.2%	9%
-20	Yes	67.2%/66.2%	1.0%	70.8%/65.8%	5.0%	20%
-30	Yes	71.1%/70.2%	0.9%	72.9%/65.0%	7.9%	33%

* This is the control sample with the conventional evaporation drying method.

Correspondingly, **Figure 3b** reveals a relatively low reflectance within the UV–vis–NIR region, indicating that the as-synthesized VO₂ thin films have a high transparency at 20 °C. Compared to the control sample (black line), all of the freeze-dried samples have a lower reflection (R) from $\lambda = 250$ to 2500 nm, which indicates that the reflection could be reduced by increasing the porosity. This is mainly due to the fact that with the reduced refractive index (n) of the porous films a lower R could be expected according to the Fresnel equation $R = (n - 1)/(n + 1)^2$. The reflectance valleys depict a blue shift (from the NIR region to the visible region) as a result of freeze-drying and a decreasing prefreezing temperature, which in turn confirms that freeze-drying after a suitable prefreezing temperature could lead to an enhancement in T_{lum} . **Figure 3c** shows that all of the freeze-dried samples have lower absorption at $\lambda > 800$ nm than the control sample. The more porous films (prefrozen at -20 °C and -30 °C, in blue and purple, respectively) show lower absorption at $\lambda > 600$ nm. The difference between these two samples and the control is small at $\lambda < 600$ nm, which may be due to the subsurface and/or intergranular scattering effect induced by porosity. It is interesting that the intersection point (where the absorption of freeze-dried samples starts to be less than that of the control sample) exhibits a blue shift that shows that with increasing porosity, less absorption would occur as a result of the decreased absorption coefficient [33,34]. The high transmittance in **Figure 3a**, low reflectance valleys in **Figure 3b**, and low absorption in **Figure 3c** prove that prefreezing and freeze-drying processes reduce the

absorption effect and reflection of VO₂ thin films in the visible range, which generate the increasing trend in T_{lum} as listed in **Table 2**.

Pre-freezing improves the transmittance in the UV and visible range (250-780 nm), which is in agreement with the calculated T_{lum} (**Table 2**). When the pre-freezing temperature is lowered, T_{lum} shows an increasing trend; this might be due to the fact that with prefreezing at lower temperature, the grains and pores of VO₂ tend to grow larger (**Figure 4**) and the calculated porosity is 2, 9, 20, and 33% for the control, nonprefrozen, -20 °C prefrozen and -30 °C prefrozen samples, respectively. It is interesting that with lower prefreezing temperatures, T_{sol} (90 °C) remains nearly the same (64.3, 65.8, and 65.0%), whereas T_{sol} (20 °C) increases from 68.5 to 70.8 to 72.9%, which suggests that with increasing porosity, the T_{sol} (20 °C) is more favorably enhanced compared with T_{sol} (90 °C), giving rise to increased ΔT_{sol} . This observation is consistent with the simulation results^[16]. Because of freeze drying, a large amount of solvent could be removed with good preservation of the inter-grain porous microstructures (**Figure 4**)^[22]. Light penetrates more easily through a medium with lower refractive index, which in this case is the air (pores), hence leading to a much higher transmittance in the freeze-dried samples (**Table 2**)^[15, 35, 36].

Figure 4: FESEM images of samples coated using 15.0 mL H₂O₂ precursor: (a) control, without prefreezing and freeze-drying; (b) freeze-dried without prefreezing; (c) prefrozen at -20 °C followed by freeze-drying and (d) prefrozen at -30 °C followed by freeze-drying.

3.2 Effects of precursor concentration and withdrawing rate on thermochromic properties

The precursor concentration was modified by changing the solvent (H₂O₂) volume from 7.5 to 17.5 mL to study the porosity effects on thermochromism at a fixed withdrawal rate of 100 mm/min. The thermochromic properties of the samples are summarized in **Table 3**. When solvent content decreases and viscosity increases, T_{lum} and T_{sol} at both temperatures (20 °C and 90 °C) decreases with higher ΔT_{sol} for control samples mainly because of the increased thickness. Similar trends are observed in freeze-dried samples with a less-steep decrease in averaged T_{lum} and a steeper increase in ΔT_{sol} than for the control samples, and this would suggest that freeze-

drying has more predominant effect than thickness in improving both T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} (**Figure 5a**). Freeze-dried samples have higher T_{lum} , T_{sol} , ΔT_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} than respective control samples; this observation is consistent with the prefreezing temperature effect as discussed in section 3.1. This could be mainly due to the fact that in the less concentrated precursor, more H₂O produced during synthesis would be frozen and sublimed to form larger pores, which can be confirmed by **Figure 6a-b** as the porosities of samples increased from 16% (7.5 mL of H₂O₂) to 44% (17.5 mL of H₂O₂). The large pore in the sample with 17.5 mL of H₂O₂ is further observed in the TEM picture (**Figure 6c**) and the inserted diffraction pattern confirms the formation of VO₂ (M) phase as shown in XRD (**Figure 2**). The diffraction rings indicate that the as-deposited samples are polycrystalline. The highest ΔT_{sol} of 12.5% can be obtained with 7.5% H₂O₂ as highlighted in **Table 3**.

Table 3: Effect of precursor concentration on thermochromic properties of thin films

H ₂ O ₂ volume (mL)	Sample type	T_{lum} (20/90 °C)	ΔT_{lum}	T_{sol} (20/90 °C)	ΔT_{sol}
7.5	Control	50.6%/52.1%	-1.5%	58.6%/53.7%	4.9%
	Freeze-fried	60.1%/58.6%	1.5%	59.0%/46.5%	12.5%
10.0	Control	54.0%/55.3%	-1.3%	62.0%/57.2%	4.8%
	Freeze-fried	60.9%/59.9%	1.0%	69.5%/60.0%	9.5%
12.5	Control	55.5%/55.4%	0.1%	61.5%/56.9%	4.6%
	Freeze-fried	60.6%/59.3%	1.3%	67.8%/59.4%	8.4%
15.0	Control	55.2%/58.2%	-3.0%	61.7%/58.8%	2.9%
	Freeze-fried	71.1%/70.2%	0.9%	72.9%/65.0%	7.9%
17.5	Control	68.7%/70.0%	-1.3%	72.4%/70.3%	2.1%
	Freeze-fried	71.6%/71.4%	0.2%	76.1%/70.5%	5.6%

Figure 5: Effect of (a) precursor concentration and (b) withdrawing rate on thermochromic properties of thin films. Average T_{lum} is the average value of T_{lum} (20 °C) and T_{lum} (90 °C).

Figure 6: FESEM images of freeze-dried samples with (a) 7.5 mL and (b) 17.5 mL of H_2O_2 , as well as (c) TEM image and (inset) SAED pattern of freeze-dried sample with 17.5 mL of H_2O_2 .

To improve ΔT_{sol} further, the thicknesses were varied by changing the withdrawal rate from 100 to 300 mm/min using 7.5 mL of H_2O_2 precursor. **Table 4** and **Figure 5b** show that when the withdrawal rate increases, higher ΔT_{sol} can be obtained with a depression in T_{lum} as a result of film thickening for both control and freeze-dried samples [32]. Freeze drying can increase T_{lum} and ΔT_{lum} , thus largely improving the ΔT_{sol} (**Figure 5b**) compared with control samples. The highlighted data in **Table 4** shows the best combination of thermochromic properties which gives $\sim 20\%$ increase in T_{lum} ($\sim 50\%$ vs. 41%) and slightly higher ΔT_{sol} (14.7% vs. 14.1%) compared with the best reported results in literature [16].

Table 4: Effect of coating speed-controlled thickness on thermochromic properties of thin films

Withdrawing rate (mm/min)	Sample type	T_{lum} (20/90 °C)	ΔT_{lum}	T_{sol} (20/90 °C)	ΔT_{sol}
100	Control	50.6%/52.1%	-1.5%	58.6%/53.7%	4.9%
	Freeze-fried	60.1%/58.6%	1.5%	59.0%/46.5%	12.5%
200	Control	46.4%/47.9%	-1.5%	50.9%/45.4%	5.5%
	Freeze-fried	55.9%/53.9%	2.0%	53.8%/40.3%	13.5%
300	Control	42.6%/44.1%	-1.5%	53.7%/47.4%	6.3%
	Freeze-fried	50.6%/49.4%	1.2%	58.9%/44.2%	14.7%

4. Conclusions

In this study, VO₂ (M) thin films were synthesized by dip-coating of VO²⁺ solution followed by freeze-drying, which rendered nanoporous structures with excellent thermochromic properties. By varying the pre-freezing temperature, and tailoring the vanadium concentration and coating thickness of the freeze-dried porous VO₂ coatings, T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} can be tuned between 50.0 to 71.6% and from 5.6 to 14.7%, respectively. An interference effect that contributed largely to the enhanced ΔT_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} with the introduction of intergrain pores was observed. Freeze-drying enhances both T_{lum} and ΔT_{sol} simultaneously compared to the same parameters for control samples and produces the most competitive result ($T_{lum} \approx 50.0\%$, $\Delta T_{sol} = 14.7\%$) in the literature.

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